

Extents of Principals' Supervisory Practices and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary Schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

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Abstract

The study examined principals' supervisory practices and teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State". Three research questions were formulated and answered in the study. The ex-post facto research design was used for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 87 principals in the 87 public secondary schools in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Principals' Supervisory Practices and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (PSPTJSQ). Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (means and standard deviation). Results obtained revealed that the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. It was also revealed that the extent to which principals practice clinical supervision and work/conferencing in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. Based on the results, it was recommended that principals should carry out effective clinical supervision practise in secondary schools in the zone; principals should also recommend teachers for professional conferences and organize workshops at regular intervals in secondary schools in the Zone as this would increase teachers' job satisfaction; principals should help teachers to learn modern pedagogical skills for effective delivery of instruction in the schools.

Keywords: Clinical supervision, conferencing, job satisfaction, supervisory practices, teachers.

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Introduction

Organizations today are increasingly placing more attention on human resources as unique assets that can provide sustained competitive advantage towards the realization of organizational goals and objectives. The dynamic nature of the environment, increasing attention on knowledge economies as the basis for organizational growth and the never-ending quest for competitive advantage has led to the increased importance of designing strategic approaches to managing staff performance in modern organizations. There has been a remarkable shift from the traditional work-centred organizations where the emphasis is always placed on work procedures, principles and standards as measures for attaining increased productivity, to modern human-centred organizations where the motivation and satisfaction of staff are seen as a pragmatic framework for improving and sustaining the performance of

organizations in the face of change and competition. Human beings in every organization are the fundamental resources for achieving the goals and objectives of the organization. The level of skills inherent in them, their motivation for the job, their levels of satisfaction on the job, determine to a large extent their level of commitment to the job, which in turn determines their level of performance in the organization.

The above expressions espouse the reasons why job satisfaction has become increasingly relevant to organizations including schools all over the world. When teachers are satisfied with their jobs in school, they tend to become happy, motivated and ready to perform at the peak of their ability. Elakes (2015) affirms that happiness and reward from work itself are obtainable from enriched jobs and that workers want to be doing jobs where such a job empowers them, giving motivation and satisfying their needs. Involving teachers in decision-making roles of the upper level, giving them more responsibilities, giving them more autonomy, to receive more opinions which enables them to evaluate their performance tend to enhance their satisfaction in the school system (Neyshabor & Rashidi, 2013). Satisfaction itself is the feeling of the individual towards his work. This feeling is a result of an assessment of the extent to which his work as a whole is capable of satisfying his/her needs. Satisfaction is related to individual factors such as personality, status and seniority, compatibility with interest and individual satisfaction in his/her life (Malik, Nawab, Naeem & Danish, 2010). Factors such as working environment, pay and promotion, job security, and level of fairness tend to have significant relationships with job satisfaction, in that they are directly related to the employees' psychological state and morale for increased performance. Thus, low job satisfaction of the teachers may lead to lack of productivity, lack of commitment, burnout, job stress, poor overall performance, and employee turnover rate (Sharif & Nazir, 2016).

From the foregoing, job satisfaction borders on the job itself and conditions surrounding the job, which if satisfactory, may motivate workers to stay on the job otherwise they go out for other jobs. Teachers may be satisfied with their jobs when they are allowed to use their full capacities without interference, giving adequate opportunities for personal and professional growth, allowed to have a say in the decisions affecting their job, given adequate feedback on their job for improvement, given more challenging responsibilities and rewards, etc. Job enrichment in the study is assessed from the level of autonomy where teachers are given the freedom to apply all their skills and abilities to teach students without interference, their level of participation in the major decisions on their job, their level of satisfaction with the conditions of service and opportunities for personal and professional growth. Giving teachers opportunities to take part in deciding issues about their job may serve as a motivating factor to boost their morale towards high performance and reduce the propensity of going out in search of better offers. Teachers' satisfaction in their jobs seems to be very essential for the school system in that it may prevent bad performance and heightened the effectiveness of the system. Job satisfaction is the feeling of the employee towards the job they do concerning conditions of work and the rewards accrued to them in return for their labour (Nyakundi, 2012).

In Cross River State, specifically in Calabar Education Zone, the issue of teachers' low job satisfaction seems to be more obvious as teachers exhibit all manner of unprofessional

behaviour in secondary schools. The researcher observes that in most secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone, teachers go to work late; hardly have complete lesson notes; some prefer to use their lesson periods for unnecessary discussions in the staff room. It is also observed that those who manage to go to classes, do not go on time, while some give students' lengthy notes without proper explanation of contents. These seem to be responsible for the observed poor performance of secondary students in internal and external examinations, and the high rate of indiscipline among secondary school students in the area. When teachers are committed to their teaching roles in schools; attend classes on time, explain lesson contents adequately using proper instructional methods, assess students using appropriate assessment tools and are committed to timely preparation of lesson notes, students' learning seems to be maximized in the three domains of educational objective and which would result in effective attainment of school goals and objectives.

Schools seem to attain their stated goals and objectives, when teachers are motivated to effectively, carry out their day-to-day activities, prepare notes of the lesson according to their scheme of work, teach students/pupils using accurate methods and procedures, attend conferences and workshops to improve instruction and use instructional material properly. This underscores the place of teachers' job satisfaction as a vital mechanism of school success and which must be sustained for the growth and goal attainment of the entire school system. It is an obvious truism that the effectiveness of teachers in their role performance or their general attitude towards their jobs is determined by the level of their job satisfaction in the school, which in turn, is a direct function of the supervisory competence of the school administrator. Charles, Chris and Kosgei (2012) submitted that school heads need to effectively supervise teachers by ensuring that teachers are observed regularly, lessons are planned on time, lessons are structured with an interesting beginning, revision of previous knowledge and teacher's use of voice variation and summary of major points at the end, teachers use backups/teaching aids properly, teachers follow up the curriculum strictly. It behoves from here that the sole determinant of teacher performance in school is the supervisory mechanism designed by the school administrators which is the school head, to oversee, direct, moderate and improve teacher's activities in the school system.

However, supervision is concerned with the provision of professional guidance and assistance to teachers and students geared towards the achievement of effective teaching and learning in the school (Osakwe, 2010). It is the way of advising, guiding, refreshing, stimulating, improving and overseeing certain groups with the hope of persuading people to resist from applying wrong procedures in carrying out their jobs at the same time try to emphasize the importance of human relations in an organization (Adenaike & Adebajo, 2000). Being that teachers' job satisfaction is a necessary tool for school goals' attainment, school heads need to employ supervisory practices that would engender high teachers' job satisfaction to secure their positive attitude and high performance as well as attainment of school goals and objectives. However, the falling level of academic achievement is attributable to teachers' non-use of verbal reinforcement strategy, unpleasant comments about learners' performances which could damage their ego. Also, the attitude of some teachers to their job which is reflected in their poor attendance to lessons, lateness to school and poor method of teaching.

Clinical supervision is a practice of supervision brought into teaching from the health or medical profession to demonstrate a supervisor-teacher relationship to improved instructional practices in schools. Gold Harmer and Cogan, in Sarfo and Cudjoe (2016), borrowed the term "Clinical Supervision" from the medical profession, where it has been in use for decades, to describe a process for improving specialized knowledge and skills of instruction practitioners. The clinical part, as indicated by them, refers to the hand-on eyes-on aspect of the supervisor who is attempting to intervene helpfully. Gold Harmer, in Sarfo and Cudjoe (2016) submitted that clinical supervision is one of the aspects of instructional supervision which draws upon data from direct observation of actual teaching and involves face-to-face interaction between the teacher and the supervisor in the course of analyzing the observed performance of the teaching. Clinical supervision is based on the assumption that without guidance and assistance, teachers are not able to change and improve (Oliva & Pawlas, 2004). Veloo, Komuji and Khalid (2013) stressed that clinical supervision administered in schools does help in increasing the teaching development of teachers while at the same time enable teachers to make improvements on their teaching practice to be more effective. Veloo, Komuji and Khalid (2013) as well as Sarfo and Cudjoe (2016) conducted different studies on clinical supervision of teachers' job performance found the clinical supervision was perceived by teachers as one of the ways of improving the quality of teachers and that the quality of education will be enhanced if supervisors adopt clinical supervision.

Workshop/conferencing as a supervisory practice or variable is very significant in boosting teachers' morale towards hard work and effective performance. Workshop as a supervisory practice is resourceful, useful and rewarding (Ekpoh & Eze, 2015). According to them, a workshop is a technique adopted by principals in which teachers are brought together in an organized way to enable the principal to communicate with them on matters of school and classroom improvement and management and most especially on methods and other areas of teaching interest that enhance teachers' performance. Ritting (2007) maintained that a workshop is one in which the individual working group brings their title, style, culture and their values together. Akinwumi (2012) asserted that the workshop is usually composed of a group of people working together for a common goal and trying to find a solution to a given problem through discussion and conferences under the supervision of resource persons or consultants. Schon (2000) opined that the common results expected from the workshop were the accumulation of materials and knowledge. Nakpodia (2006) opines that the workshop technique is another form of supervisory strategy through which the teaching-learning process can be improved. Sule (2013), James, David and Thinguri (2014) and Akpan and Ita (2015) conducted similar researches on supervisory practices and teachers' job performance and found that workshop/conferencing is one of the feasible supervisory that enhance teachers' job effectiveness in school, as well as boost their morale for improved performance in the school system.

From the foregoing, it could be deduced that the application of an appropriate supervisory approach in schools can enhance the level of teachers' job satisfaction in the school system. It implies that the application of appropriate supervisory practices may boost teachers' level of satisfaction and enhance their teachers in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River

State. Given the observed poor of teachers' job performance in the Zone, it becomes necessary to examine principals' supervisory practices and teachers' job satisfaction in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Statement of the problem

The success of any school system largely depends on the level at which teachers carry out their instructional roles in schools. No school system can perform maximally when teachers are not committed to the effective discharge of their teaching roles in schools. One of the fundamental issues contending with the success of the secondary school system and the attainment of its stated goals and objectives in Cross River State seems to be teachers' low level of job satisfaction, which has overtime manifested in all manner of unprofessional work behaviour exhibited by teachers in the school system. This problem seems to be specifically heightened in Calabar Education Zone where the researcher observes that teachers go to work late; hardly have complete lesson notes; some prefer to use their lesson periods for unnecessary discussions in the staff room. It is also observed that those who manage to go to classes, do not go on time, while some give students' lengthy notes without proper explanation of contents. These seem to be responsible for the observed poor performance of secondary students in internal and external examinations, and the high rate of indiscipline among secondary school students in the area.

This has over time attracted prompt measures such as increasing teachers' incentive packages, intensifying teachers' training and providing basic school infrastructure in the area by the Cross River State government. Despite these laudable measures the trend persists in secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone, and the researcher is worried about this ugly situation. Teachers may be enthused to perform better when the principals can adopt ineffective supervisory practices or approaches in the school system. Given this scenario, it becomes necessary to raise the question: How do principals' supervisory practices relate to teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State?

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to examine principals' supervisory practices and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to find out;

1. The extent of teachers' job satisfaction in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State
2. The extent to which principals practice clinical supervision in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State
3. The extent to which principal practice workshop/conferencing in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Research questions

The following questions were raised to direct the study

1. What is the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State?
2. To what extent do principals practice clinical supervision in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State?
3. To what extent do principals practice workshop/conferencing in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State?

Methods

This research work was conducted in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The ex-post facto research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised of all the 87 principals in the 87 public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The 87 principals of the 87 public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State was used as a sample for this study. The sampling technique adopted for the study was census. This a technique was used by the researcher to study the entire population because of the small population involved in the study and the need to include all the subjects of the study for adequate and accurate generalization. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Principals' Supervisory Practices and Teachers' Job satisfaction Questionnaire (PSPTJSQ)". The questionnaire was divided into two sections - A and B. Section A was designed to obtain information from respondents based on demographic variables of sex, age, educational qualifications and years of experience, while Section B was designed to obtain information from respondents regarding principals' supervisory practice and teachers job satisfaction respectively. Six (6) items on a modified four-point Likert scale were designed to measure each variable. Two teachers from each of the 87 schools responded to the questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts and tested for reliability using the Cronbach Alpha approach. The reliability coefficient of .79 proved that the instrument was internally consistent. All the instruments were retrieved and used for analysis. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation).

Results**Research question 1**

What is the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State? The responses to this research question are presented in Table 1. The result of the analysis in Table 1 shows that all the items have mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.50. Given that the average mean and standard deviation are 2.12 and 0.46 there is a high degree of acceptance that the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Calabar

Education Zone of Cross River State is low. This means that secondary school teachers are not satisfied with their jobs in public secondary schools in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the responses on the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	I feel very happy working in this school.	2.44	.345	Disagreed
2	I am very satisfied with my job in the school.	2.01	.522	Disagreed
3	Teachers hardly complain of their job in the school	2.22	.341	Disagreed
4	I am aware that some teachers are very happy working in my school	2.23	.448	Disagreed
5	There is low burnout among teachers because of principals' approach in school supervision.	1.74	.612	Disagreed
6	Teachers are very committed to their work in the school	2.07	.532	Disagreed
	Average means and Std. Dev.	2.12	.466	

Research question 2

To what extent do principals practice clinical supervision in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State? The responses to this research question are presented in Table 2. The result of the analysis in Table 2 shows that all the items have mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.50. Given that the average mean and standard deviation are 2.30 and .616 there is a high degree of acceptance that the extent to which principals practice clinical supervision in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. This means that principals in public secondary school teachers in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State do not effectively practice clinical supervision in their schools.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the responses on the extent to which principals practice clinical supervision in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
7	Teachers are always guided on improved instructional practices in the school	2.23	.552	Disagreed
8	Principal on regular basis invites teachers who perform poorly on face-to-face interaction to improve their performance	2.44	.761	Disagreed
9	The principal creates interpersonal relationships with teachers in the school.	2.28	.662	Disagreed
10	Teachers are always happy to share their instructional difficulties with the principal.	2.46	.432	Disagreed
11	Teachers who perform poorly in the classroom are always encouraged by the principal	2.33	.621	Disagreed
12	Post observation conference always organized after every supervision exercise to guide teachers	2.08	.673	Disagreed
	Average means and Std. Dev.	2.30	.616	

Research question 3

To what extent do principals practice workshops/conferences in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State? The responses to this research question are presented in Table 3. The result of the analysis in Table 1 shows that all the items except item 17 have mean scores below the criterion mean of 2.50. Given that the average mean and standard deviation are 2.25 and .557 there is a high degree of acceptance that the extent to which principals practice workshop/conferencing in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. This means that principals in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State do not effectively, practice workshop/conferencing in their schools.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the responses on the extent to which principals practice workshop/conferencing in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

S/N	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
13	The principal encourages teachers to attend workshops.	2.20	.451	Disagreed
14	He recommends teachers for conferences and workshops outside the school annually	2.47	.623	Disagreed
15	The principal organizes workshops for teachers' improvement.	2.22	.433	Disagreed
16	Teachers are given an allowance for attending conferences	2.01	.474	Disagreed
17	Teachers are always recommended for national conferences and workshops.	2.51	.723	Agreed
18	Teachers' instructional difficulties and suggestions are always treated in a round table meeting with other staff.	2.06	.641	Disagreed
	Average means and Std. Dev.	2.25	.557	

Discussion

The result of research question 1 revealed that the extent to which teachers are satisfied with their jobs in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. This result means that teachers are not happy with the nature of their teaching jobs in secondary schools in the Zone. This may largely account for the observed poor performance of teachers in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. This result is in line with the opinion of Elakes (2015) who stressed that happiness and reward from work itself are obtainable from enriched jobs and that workers want to be doing jobs where such a job empowers them, giving motivation and satisfying their needs. Neyshabor and Rashidi (2013) also added that involving teachers in decision-making roles of the upper level, giving them more responsibilities, giving them more autonomy, to receive more opinion which enables them to evaluate their performance tend to enhance their satisfaction in the school system.

The result of research question 2 revealed that the extent to which principals practice clinical supervision in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. This means that principals in public secondary school teachers in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State do not effectively practice clinical supervision in their schools. This result suggests that principals

in the zone do hold pre-observation and post-observation conferences with teachers, do not carry out collegial discussion sessions with teachers and do not give teachers opportunities to discuss their instructional difficulties with them in the schools. This may be responsible for the observed level of teachers' job dissatisfaction in the Zone. When teachers are given opportunities to share their difficulties, feeling and make suggestions towards improvement of instructional process in school, they tend to feel more recognized in the system, which can trigger high job satisfaction and performance among them in the school. This result supports the findings of Veloo, Komuji and Khalid (2013), as well as Sarfo and Cudjoe (2016) which all found that clinical supervision was perceived by teachers as one of the ways of improving the quality of teachers and that the quality of education will be enhanced if supervisors adopt clinical supervision.

The result of research question 3 revealed that the extent to which principals practice workshop/conferencing in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. This means that principals in public secondary schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State do not effectively, practice workshop/conferencing in their schools. This result suggests that teachers are not sponsored for conferences, are not regular exposed to professional workshop programmes that can help them build their intellectual prowess and instructional proficiency for improvement in their job performance in the schools. Acquisition of new skills, knowledge and ideas in a given area, is in itself, a satisfier and a motivator. This means that given teachers opportunities to acquire new skills can enhance their level of satisfaction and performance in the school system. This result supports the findings of Sule (2013), James, David and Thinguri (2014) and Akpan and Ita (2015) who conducted similar researches on supervisory practices and teachers' job performance and found that workshop/conferencing is one of the feasible supervisory that enhance teachers' job effectiveness in school, as well as boost their morale for improved performance in the school system.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the extent of teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low. It is also concluded that the extent to which principals practice clinical supervision and work/conferencing in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State is low.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the research findings the following recommendations are made.

1. Principals in secondary schools should carry out effective clinical supervision practise in secondary schools in the Zone as this would give teachers a sense of belonging, fulfilment and achievement to improve teaching and learning activities in the area.
2. Principals should recommend teachers for professional conferences and organize regular workshops at regular intervals in secondary schools in the Zone. This would

increase teachers job satisfaction, help them to learn modern pedagogical skills for effective delivery of instruction in the schools

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